

Correcting socioeconomic bias in mobile phone mobility estimates using multilevel regression and poststratification

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Abstract

Call detail records (CDR) from mobile phone networks are widely used to study human mobility, but the user population of any single carrier is not representative of the general population. Using data from a major Chilean carrier for the Santiago Metropolitan Region (47 comunas, 730 census zones) covering approximately 118,400 user-month-weekday observations in 2016, we document non-uniform penetration rates across socioeconomic groups: the highest-income group (ABC1) has the lowest penetration (2.2%), while middle-income groups C2 (6.9%) and D (5.9%) are overrepresented. Because mobility patterns vary with socioeconomic status, this compositional bias distorts aggregate mobility metrics such as the radius of gyration.

We use multilevel regression and poststratification (MRP) as a correction for sample bias. Specifically, we fit a Bayesian multilevel model of individual-level mobility as a function of socioeconomic group, gender, and geography, allowing for partial pooling across comunas. We then poststratify the model predictions to align with the demographic composition reported in the census. The resulting MRP-adjusted estimate of the average radius of gyration is 20.2km, 17% lower than the naive CDR-based estimate of 24.2km. Cross-validation on held-out comunas yields a root mean squared error of 0.71 on the log scale, and sensitivity analyses indicate that the comuna-level random intercept is a key component of the model. This application illustrates how MRP can be used to correct CDR-derived mobility estimates for non-representative user populations.

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Keywords: call detail records, human mobility, multilevel regression and poststratification, socioeconomic bias, radius of gyration, Bayesian hierarchical models

1 Introduction

Mobile phone data, particularly Call Detail Records (CDR), have transformed the study of human mobility (González, Hidalgo, and Barabási, 2008; Barbosa et al., 2018). Passive observation of millions of users over extended periods enables measurement of mobility patterns at unprecedented spatial and temporal resolution, with applications ranging from urban planning (Lenormand et al., 2015) to epidemic modelling (Wesolowski, Eagle, Tatem, et al., 2012; Tizzoni et al., 2014; Gozzi et al., 2021) and poverty estimation (Blumenstock, Cadamuro, and On, 2015).

Despite these advances, a fundamental limitation of CDR data is that the user base of any single mobile carrier is not necessarily a random sample of the population (Ricciato et al., 2017; Vanhoof et al., 2018). Prior work has documented this primarily in low-penetration settings, where mobile phone *ownership* itself is socioeconomically stratified: phone owners in Rwanda and Kenya are wealthier, better educated, and more predominantly male than the general population (Blumenstock and Eagle, 2010; Wesolowski, Eagle, Noor, et al., 2013a), and resulting biases propagate into modelled outbreak dynamics (Chin et al., 2025). However, in high-penetration markets such as Chile, where mobile subscriptions exceed one per capita (Pew Research Center, 2016), the ownership channel is largely closed. The relevant bias instead concerns *carrier-specific representation*: the user base of any single operator is a non-random subset of the near-universally phone-owning population, selected by carrier preference, contract type, and voice-call usage patterns. The direction and magnitude of this bias is an empirical question that depends on the local market structure.

The development of methods to correct for representativeness bias in mobility metrics research has received limited attention. Although the presence of bias in mobile phone data has been recognized since the early use of Call Detail Records (CDRs), and has been extensively quantified and documented (Wesolowski, Eagle, Noor, et al., 2013b; Zhao et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2024; Cabrera and Rowe, 2025), relatively few studies propose concrete methods to correct these biases. Existing approaches often rely on simple rescaling of observations to improve representativeness (Wesolowski, Eagle, Noor, et al., 2013b; Meppelink et al., 2020), but methodological developments specifically tailored to CDR data remain limited.

More advanced approaches have been developed in related contexts. For example, some studies estimate bias and infer relative population changes over time using difference-in-differences frameworks without requiring ground truth data (Pestre, Letouzé, and Zagheni,

2020). However, these methods are primarily designed to capture temporal dynamics rather than to correct representativeness bias in mobility metrics. Similarly, work addressing temporal bias in GPS-based mobility data has been proposed (Sanchez et al., 2026), but with a different objective.

In other domains, bias correction methods such as Multilevel Regression with Post-stratification (MRP) have been widely applied (Wang et al., 2015) and offer a promising framework for addressing representativeness issues. However, such approaches have not yet been adapted to CDR-based mobility data. Some studies have applied post-stratification techniques to adjust indicators derived from mobile phone surveys, such as total fertility rate (Sánchez-Páez et al., 2023), but these approaches do not incorporate a regression component.

Recent studies on mobile phone-based mobility data continue to highlight bias as a persistent issue, emphasizing the need for new methodological developments (Li et al., 2024; Gauvin, 2024). This is particularly important given the increasing use of human mobility data in policy and research. Uncorrected biases may lead to misleading conclusions and sub-optimal policy decisions. If mobility patterns differ systematically across the demographic groups that are differentially represented, the bias in aggregate estimates can be substantial.

In this paper, we make three contributions. First, we quantify the representativeness bias in CDR data from a major Chilean carrier by comparing the demographic composition of CDR users with the 2017 national census for the Santiago Metropolitan Region. Second, we propose multilevel regression and poststratification (MRP) as a principled statistical correction. MRP, widely used in political science for small-area estimation from non-representative surveys (Park, Gelman, and Bafumi, 2004; Lax and Phillips, 2009; Gelman and Little, 1997), combines a multilevel model that relates the outcome to demographic and geographic predictors with poststratification weights derived from census population counts. Third, we apply this framework to the radius of gyration, a standard mobility metric, and show that MRP-corrected estimates differ meaningfully from naive CDR averages, particularly at disaggregated levels.

2 Data and Context

2.1 Call detail records

We use CDR data from the former Telefónica Chile mobile network (Movistar), one of the country’s three major mobile carriers, covering May to July 2016. At that time, Telefónica held approximately 31.9% of Chile’s mobile market. Mobile penetration was about 127

subscriptions per 100 inhabitants, implying that basic mobile access was effectively universal (Subsecretaría de Telecomunicaciones de Chile, 2016). The main representativeness concern is therefore not phone ownership, but which users are captured in this carrier’s voice-call records. The original dataset contains anonymised voice-call records for users in three Chilean metropolitan regions. We restrict the analysis to the Santiago Metropolitan Region (Región Metropolitana), where census and socioeconomic data are most complete.

For each user, we know the antenna location of each call, the time, and call metadata (placed or received, duration) as well as the socioeconomic group (GSE) and gender. We restrict the sample to Chilean nationals with a valid GSE classification and at least one call per day on average, following standard filtering practices to ensure reliable location estimates (Pappalardo, Simini, et al., 2015). This activity threshold is relatively aggressive and may itself introduce socioeconomic bias if call frequency correlates with GSE; we return to this point in Section 7. After filtering, the dataset contains approximately 118,400 user-month-weekday observations.

2.2 Construction of mobility metrics and spatial assignment for MRP

Home locations are assigned based on the most frequent antenna during evening hours (20:00–06:00), a standard approach in the CDR literature (Vanhoof et al., 2018; Pappalardo, Ferres, et al., 2021). From the sequence of antenna locations, we compute the radius of gyration (ROG), i.e the characteristic distance travelled from an individual’s centre of mass, measuring the spatial extent of mobility (González, Hidalgo, and Barabási, 2008) for each user in each month, separately for weekdays and weekends.

In the framework introduced here, we operate at the level of cells defined by the unique combination of distrito, GSE, gender, month, and weekday/weekend. Radius of gyration is aggregated at this level; more exactly, we consider the mean of the log-transformed radius of gyration within each cell.

For the MRP framework, each user must be assigned to a distrito. We consider two alternative spatial assignment strategies: (i) a point-in-district approach, where each user is assigned to the distrito of their home antenna; and (ii) an area-weighted H3 hexagon approach around each antenna. As shown in Appendix D.1, the area-weighted H3 redistribution yields district-level mean radius of gyration values that are virtually identical to the baseline specification, with a Pearson correlation of $r = 0.9999$ and a maximum posterior mean shift of 0.036 log-units. Overall, both user assignment strategies lead to highly consistent distributions.

2.3 Socioeconomic data

Socio-economic data are derived from two sources. The first is the CDR-based GSE, a label assigned by Telefónica at the individual level (originally defined at an area level but provided at the user level in the data). The second is the GSE distribution derived from an index called ISMT (defined below), which provides the census-level population benchmark used to correct for representativeness bias.

Individual GSE from CDR. Each user in the CDR dataset is assigned a socioeconomic group (GSE: ABC1, C2, C3, D, E) by Telefonica based on the user’s salary information. This per-user attribute is included in the raw CDR extract and is used directly as a predictor variable in the MRP model. We do not derive or impute individual GSE from any external source.

Population GSE distribution from ISMT. To construct the poststratification frame, we require the true distribution of GSE in the population by geographic unit. For this purpose, we use the `ismtchile` R package (Araya, 2023), which provides the Territorial Sociomaterial Index (ISMT, *Índice Socio Material Territorial*), version 3, based on the 2017 census. The ISMT reports household counts by socioeconomic group at the census-zone level (*redcodes*, roughly equivalent to census tracts), which allows us to derive the relative distribution of GSE within each unit rather than exact counts at the district level. We aggregate these data from *redcodes* to census districts (*distritos*) to obtain the conditional distribution $P(\text{GSE} \mid \text{distrito})$. This distribution, expressed as proportions of individuals across GSE categories within each district, is then used in the poststratification frame alongside census population counts and gender proportions (Section 4.3)..

2.4 Census data

We use the 2017 Chilean Census of Population and Housing (Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas, 2017) for two purposes: (1) to compare the demographic composition of CDR users with the true population, and (2) to construct the poststratification frame for MRP. The census provides person-level records with sex and geographic identifiers (region, provincia, comuna), which we aggregate to obtain population counts by gender and geographic unit.

2.5 Geographic units

Our analysis operates at three nested geographic scales within the Santiago Metropolitan Region:

- **Comuna** (47 units): Administrative divisions, the primary unit for the random intercept in our multilevel model.
- **Distrito censal** (329 units): Census districts, the fine geographic unit for the post-stratification frame. Each distrito nests within exactly one comuna.
- **Zona censal / redcode** (730 units): Census zones from ISMT, the finest level at which GSE classifications are available. Each zona nests within exactly one distrito; we aggregate GSE proportions from zonas to distritos.

3 Quantifying representativeness bias

To quantify the representativeness bias, we compare the demographic composition of CDR users with census population counts. For each redcode, we compute the number of CDR users by GSE group and compare with the census population in the same categories.

Table 1 presents the aggregate results for the Santiago Metropolitan Region.

Table 1: CDR vs. census composition and penetration rates by GSE group, Santiago Metropolitan Region.

GSE	CDR (%)	Census (%)	Penetration
ABC1	14.4	31.1	0.022
C2	23.1	15.7	0.069
C3	26.7	25.0	0.050
D	30.0	23.6	0.059
E	5.7	4.6	0.058

Contrary to what one might expect, the highest-income group (ABC1) is the most *under*-represented in the CDR data: it accounts for 14.4% of CDR users but 31.1% of the census population, yielding the lowest penetration rate (0.022). Middle-income groups C2 and D are overrepresented, with penetration rates of 0.069 and 0.059, respectively. The penetration rate is not monotonically related to socioeconomic status; rather, C2 has the highest rate, with a factor of $3.1\times$ between the highest (C2) and lowest (ABC1) penetration rates.

Figure 1 shows the CDR versus census GSE proportions at the redcode level, confirming that the bias is pervasive across geographic units.

Figure 1: CDR vs. census GSE proportions at the redcode level.

Because mobility metrics vary with socioeconomic status (Figure 2 shows the distribution of radius of gyration by GSE, with naive averages decreasing from ABC1 at 27.4 km to E at 21.5 km), this compositional bias translates directly into distorted aggregate mobility estimates.

Figure 2: Distribution of radius of gyration by GSE group.

4 Multilevel Regression and Poststratification

4.1 MRP framework

MRP builds on earlier work on poststratification and hierarchical regression, with its modern formulation usually traced to Gelman and Little (1997) and its influential application to small-area public-opinion estimation developed by Park, Gelman, and Bafumi (2004). It was later widely adopted in political science for estimating state-level public opinion from national surveys (Lax and Phillips, 2009; Buttcie and Highton, 2013). To our knowledge, we are the first to adapt this framework to correct mobility estimates from non-representative CDR data.

4.2 Model specification

The model is fit on cell-level summaries: one observation per unique combination of distrito, GSE, gender, month, and weekday/weekend. Let y_{ijkmt} denote the mean log radius of gyration for the cell defined by distrito i , GSE group j , gender k , month m , and weekday indicator t . Our model is:

$$y_{ijkmt} = \mu + \beta_j^{\text{GSE}} + \beta_k^{\text{gender}} + \beta_{jk}^{\text{GSE} \times \text{gender}} + \beta_t^{\text{weekday}} + \beta_m^{\text{month}} + \alpha_{c(i)}^{\text{comuna}} + \varepsilon_{ijkmt} \quad (1)$$

where:

- μ is the overall intercept.
- β_j^{GSE} captures the main effect of socioeconomic group ($j \in \{\text{ABC1}, \text{C2}, \text{C3}, \text{D}, \text{E}\}$).
- β_k^{gender} captures the main effect of gender.
- $\beta_{jk}^{\text{GSE} \times \text{gender}}$ captures the interaction.
- β_t^{weekday} and β_m^{month} control for temporal variation.
- $\alpha_{c(i)}^{\text{comuna}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{comuna}}^2)$ is a random intercept for the comuna containing distrito i , capturing unobserved geographic heterogeneity across the 47 comunas of the Santiago Metropolitan Region.
- $\varepsilon_{ijkmt} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2/n_{ijkmt})$ is the residual, where n_{ijkmt} is the number of users in the cell. This observation-level weighting is equivalent to case-weighted regression: cells with more users contribute more to the likelihood in proportion to their precision. Appendix D.2 shows that results are substantively unchanged relative to unweighted

estimation (maximum posterior mean shift of 0.104 log-units; all 94% credible intervals overlap).

The outcome is log-transformed to accommodate the right-skewed, strictly positive distribution of radius of gyration. The model is fit in Bambi (Capretto et al., 2022), a Python interface to PyMC (Salvatier, Wiecki, and Fonnesbeck, 2016), using the `numpyro` backend (JAX-accelerated NUTS) with 4 chains of 2,000 post-warmup draws each.

4.3 Poststratification

Let \mathcal{J} index the cells of the poststratification frame, defined by the cross-classification of distrito \times GSE \times gender. For each cell j , we obtain the posterior predictive distribution $\tilde{y}_j^{(s)}$ for draw $s = 1, \dots, S$ from the fitted model (evaluated at reference conditions: weekday, month 5). The poststratification weights N_j are the census person counts in cell j , constructed under a conditional independence assumption:

$$N_j = N_{\text{distrito}} \times P(\text{GSE} \mid \text{distrito}) \times P(\text{gender} \mid \text{comuna}). \quad (2)$$

Here N_{distrito} is the number of persons in the census district from the 2017 census microdata, and $P(\text{GSE} \mid \text{distrito})$ is obtained by aggregating ISMT household-level GSE counts across the census zones within each district. Because GSE is an area-level classification, the conditional independence between GSE and gender in equation (2) holds by construction: the GSE composition of a census district does not vary by gender.

The MRP-corrected estimate for any domain D (e.g., a GSE group, a comuna, or the overall population) is:

$$\hat{\theta}_D^{(s)} = \frac{\sum_{j \in D} N_j \exp(\tilde{y}_j^{(s)})}{\sum_{j \in D} N_j}, \quad (3)$$

where the $\exp(\cdot)$ back-transforms from the log scale. Uncertainty is propagated by computing $\hat{\theta}_D^{(s)}$ for each posterior draw. The poststratification frame contains 3,282 cells covering a total census population of 6,217,025 persons.

4.4 Geography-only variant

The framework described above requires individual-level SES labels for CDR users, as provided here by Telefónica’s salary-based classification. When such labels are unavailable, a reduced model retaining only geographic post-stratification can still partially correct representativeness bias, provided that SES is spatially clustered (a condition we verify formally

before fitting the model as explained below). In that case, the geography-only multilevel model replaces the full specification in equation (1) with:

$$y_{imt} = \mu + \beta_t^{\text{weekday}} + \beta_m^{\text{month}} + \alpha_{c(i)}^{\text{comuna}} + \varepsilon_{imt}, \quad (4)$$

retaining the weekday and month controls and the commune random intercept, but dropping the GSE and gender fixed effects and their interaction. The same poststratification formula (equations (2) and (3)) applies unchanged: census weights still vary by (distrito, GSE, gender); only the model predictions (now depending solely on commune) are simplified.

To assess whether CDR coverage bias has a geographic SES structure in Santiago, we regress the district-level log CDR/census ratio on the district’s GSE composition:

$$\log\left(\frac{n_i^{\text{CDR}}}{n_i^{\text{census}}}\right) = \gamma_0 + \sum_j \gamma_j P(\text{GSE} = j \mid i) + \eta_i, \quad (5)$$

estimated by OLS across all 329 Santiago districts (ABC1 as reference category). The regression explains $R^2 = 0.31$ of district-level log-ratio variance (F -test $p = 5.7 \times 10^{-25}$), with significant coefficients for C3 ($\hat{\gamma} = -4.75$, $p < 0.001$) and E ($\hat{\gamma} = -2.37$, $p = 0.007$). Districts with a higher share of lower-income residents have systematically lower CDR coverage relative to their census population, and this pattern is spatially structured. Geographic post-stratification can therefore partially absorb SES-related coverage bias.

5 Results

We begin by presenting the results of the full model, followed by a comparison with a geography-only specification in Section 5.5.

5.1 Model diagnostics

The full model (62 parameters: 15 fixed effects and 47 comuna-level intercepts) shows good convergence across all Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) runs: all parameters show good convergence diagnostics, with Gelman–Rubin statistics $\hat{R} \leq 1.01$, a minimum bulk effective sample size (ESS) of 782, and a minimum tail ESS of 1,534. No divergent transitions are observed.

Figure 3: Posterior distributions of fixed effects on $\log(\text{ROG})$. Points show posterior means; thick and thin bars show 50% and 94% highest density intervals. GSE effects are relative to ABC1 (reference).

5.2 Fixed effects

Figure 3 shows the posterior distributions of the fixed effects. Relative to ABC1 (the reference category), the GSE coefficients on the log scale are: C2 +0.175 [0.134, 0.216], C3 +0.188 [0.146, 0.228], D +0.129 [0.090, 0.171], and E -0.135 [-0.175, -0.094]. After controlling for comuna, C2, C3, and D all have *higher* conditional ROG than ABC1; only E is substantially lower. This contrasts with the raw (unconditional) pattern in which ABC1 has the highest naive average. The reversal reflects geographic confounding: ABC1 zones are concentrated in eastern Santiago comunas (e.g., Las Condes, Vitacura, Providencia) that are relatively distant from the city centre, inflating raw ROG through longer commutes. Once the model conditions on comuna, this spatial advantage disappears and the within-comuna GSE gradient favours middle-income groups. Men have higher mobility than women, consistent with prior findings (Gauvin et al., 2020). The GSE \times gender interactions are small; model comparison (Section 6) confirms that their contribution is marginal.

5.3 Random effects

The comuna-level random intercept standard deviation (σ_{comuna}) is estimated at 0.186 [0.148, 0.227], indicating meaningful geographic heterogeneity in mobility beyond what is captured by the fixed effects. As shown in the sensitivity analysis (Section 6), removing the comuna random intercept substantially degrades model fit.

5.4 MRP-corrected vs. naive estimates

Table 2 compares naive CDR averages with MRP-corrected estimates. At the overall level, the MRP-corrected average ROG is 20.23 km [19.84, 20.58], 16.6% lower than the naive CDR average of 24.24 km. By GSE group, the MRP-corrected gradient is C2 (21.9 km) > C3 (21.5 km) > ABC1 (20.2 km) > D (19.6 km) \gg E (14.4 km). Shifts from naive to corrected range from -2.5 km (C3) to -7.2 km (ABC1). Notably, the MRP-corrected ranking places C2, not ABC1, as the group with the highest spatial extent of mobility, suggesting that middle-income groups in Santiago have the greatest true mobility once representativeness bias is removed. By gender, women shift from 21.9 to 18.7 km and men from 26.6 to 21.8 km.

Table 2: Naive CDR average vs. MRP-corrected radius of gyration (km) by GSE group and overall. Credible intervals are 94% HDI.

Group	Naive	MRP [94% CI]	Shift
ABC1	27.4	20.2 [19.7, 20.8]	-7.2
C2	25.2	21.9 [21.3, 22.4]	-3.4
C3	24.0	21.5 [20.9, 22.1]	-2.5
D	23.1	19.6 [19.2, 20.1]	-3.5
E	21.5	14.4 [14.0, 14.7]	-7.1
Overall	24.2	20.2 [19.8, 20.6]	-4.0

Note that the naive-to-MRP comparison conflates two effects: demographic reweighting and the back-transformation from the log scale (geometric vs. arithmetic mean). Both contribute to the downward shift.

Figure 4: Average radius of gyration by GSE: naive CDR average (grey) vs. MRP-corrected estimate (blue, with 94% credible intervals).

At the comuna level, the mean shift is -4.7 km with a maximum absolute shift of 19.8 km. Comunas whose demographic composition diverges most from the census experience the largest corrections (Figure 5). The heterogeneity of the correction can be seen in the maps of Figure 6.

Figure 5: Naive vs. MRP-corrected average radius of gyration by comuna.

Figure 6: Choropleth maps of the Santiago Metropolitan Region showing (left) naive CDR average, (centre) MRP-corrected average, and (right) the shift from naive to corrected radius of gyration by comuna.

5.5 Geography-only MRP

The geography-only model (equation (4)) converges well ($\hat{R}_{\max} = 1.01$, zero divergent transitions, comuna random-effect standard deviation $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{comuna}} = 0.183$, comparable to 0.186 for the full model). Table 3 and Figure 7 compare the three estimators.

Table 3: Overall radius of gyration under three estimators. Credible intervals are 94% HDI.

Estimator	Mean (km)	CI _{3%}	CI _{97%}
Naive CDR	24.24	–	–
Geography-only MRP	19.40	19.06	19.74
Full MRP (SES + geography)	20.23	19.70	20.77

Geography-only MRP reduces the overall estimate from 24.24 km to 19.40 km [19.06, 19.74], moving in the correct direction relative to the full MRP target of 20.23 km. The aggregate correction (4.84 km) is slightly larger than the full model’s (4.01 km) because commune-level predictions do not account for within-commune SES heterogeneity: in low-mobility communes that house some higher-SES residents, those residents are assigned the same uniformly low commune prediction, whereas the full model would give them a higher one. By GSE group (Figure 7), the geography-only estimator undercorrects for the lowest-income group (GSE E: 18.16 km vs. the full MRP target of 14.39 km, recovering only 47% of the needed correction) while overcorrecting for C2 and C3. Individual SES data are therefore essential for a calibrated correction, particularly at the extremes of the income distribution.

Figure 7: Radius of gyration by GSE group for three estimators: naive CDR average (red), geography-only MRP (orange, 94% credible intervals), and full MRP with SES and geography (green, 94% credible intervals). Geography-only MRP corrects the aggregate bias in the right direction but misses the extreme deficit of the lowest-income group (GSE E).

6 Validation

6.1 Cross-validation

We perform five-fold cross-validation grouped by comuna: in each fold, 20% of comunas (and all their constituent cells) are held out, the model is fit on the remaining 80%, and predictions are generated for the held-out comunas. This tests the model’s ability to generalise to new geographic units, which is the key requirement for poststratification. For a held-out comuna with no training observations, the random intercept is drawn from the posterior of the group-level distribution, $\alpha_{j^*} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \hat{\sigma}_{\text{comuna}}^2)$, marginalising over the unknown group effect rather than setting it to zero. Appendix D.3 demonstrates this empirically on five held-out comunas: the 94% prediction intervals achieve 91% empirical coverage, and coverage at the GSE-group and comuna levels is 100%.

Across folds, the mean RMSE on the log scale is 0.709 at the cell level, corresponding roughly to predictions being off by a factor of $\exp(0.709) \approx 2.0$ on the original km scale. The 94% credible interval coverage at the cell level is 43.0%, well below the nominal 94%. This low coverage reflects the fact that the model captures systematic variation (fixed effects and random intercepts) but not the substantial within-cell individual heterogeneity.

Because MRP targets group-level aggregates rather than individual cell predictions, coverage improves at higher levels of aggregation (e.g., by comuna or GSE group), which is the relevant scale for poststratification.

6.2 Sensitivity to model specification

We compare three model specifications using approximate leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO-CV) via Pareto-smoothed importance sampling (Vehtari, Gelman, and Gabry, 2017). LOO-CV estimates out of sample predictive performance by iteratively evaluating how well the model predicts each observation when it is left out of the fitting process. Model comparison is based on the expected log predictive density (ELPD), where higher (less negative) values indicate better predictive accuracy. We also report the standard error (SE) of the ELPD estimate and the effective number of parameters (p_{LOO}), which reflects model flexibility.

1. **No interaction:** GSE + gender + comuna intercept (ELPD = $-20,411.8$, SE = 132.9, $p_{\text{loo}} = 55.0$).
2. **With interaction:** adds GSE \times gender (ELPD = $-20,411.9$, SE = 132.8, $p_{\text{loo}} = 59.1$).
3. **No random intercept:** fixed effects only (ELPD = $-20,966.8$, SE = 129.3, $p_{\text{loo}} = 14.8$).

The two models with the comuna random intercept perform comparably (ELPD difference < 1 , well within one standard error); the interaction adds four effective parameters for negligible improvement. The model without the random intercept is substantially worse. Indeed, the difference in ELPD (≈ 555) is far larger than its associated standard error (129), indicating decisive evidence in favor of the model with comuna random effects. We conclude that the comuna random intercept is essential, while the GSE \times gender interaction has marginal benefit. We retain the interaction for theoretical completeness.

6.3 Direction of correction

MRP-corrected estimates are lower than naive averages across all GSE groups and 46 of 47 comunas; a single small comuna shows a marginal upward shift of 1.3 km. This is consistent with the joint effect of demographic reweighting (correcting for non-uniform penetration) and the log-scale back-transformation, which yields population-weighted geometric rather than arithmetic means.

7 Discussion

7.1 When does the correction matter?

The magnitude of the MRP correction depends on two factors: the degree of demographic non-representativeness and the strength of the association between demographics and the mobility outcome. In our setting, both are substantial: CDR penetration rates vary by a factor of $3.1\times$ across GSE groups (C2/ABC1), and the GSE gradient in conditional mobility is strong. The correction is most consequential at the aggregate level (16.6% overall) and for comunas whose demographic composition diverges most from the census (maximum shift of 19.8 km).

For within-group analyses (e.g., comparing weekday vs. weekend mobility for ABC1 users), the correction matters less because the model conditions on the group membership.

7.2 Generalisability

The MRP framework is general and can be applied to CDR data from any setting where (1) the non-representativeness can be characterised with respect to known demographic variables, and (2) census or survey data provide the population distribution of those variables. The approach extends naturally to other mobility metrics (we show results for entropy and unique locations in the Appendix) and to other outcomes derived from CDR data.

When individual SES labels are unavailable, the geography-only variant (Sections 4.4 and 5.5) offers a practical alternative: it requires only census population counts by geographic unit, with no individual-level SES classification from the operator. In cities with strong residential SES segregation (such as Santiago, where district GSE composition explains 31% of variation in district-level CDR coverage bias), the commune random intercept absorbs much of the SES-related coverage heterogeneity, and the aggregate correction is substantial. The residual gap relative to full MRP is concentrated at the extremes of the income distribution, and researchers should bear this limitation in mind when SES-disaggregated estimates are the primary target.

7.3 Limitations

Several limitations should be noted. First, our analysis is restricted to the Santiago Metropolitan Region; generalisation to other Chilean regions or countries remains to be tested. Second, the activity filter (at least one call per day on average) is relatively aggressive and may introduce its own socioeconomic bias if call frequency correlates with GSE. Heavy voice callers may differ systematically from light callers, and this selection operates prior to our MRP

correction. Third, our socioeconomic classification is at the area level (census zone) rather than the individual level. While this is standard in Chilean research (Araya, 2023), it introduces ecological fallacy concerns. Fourth, we observe data from a single carrier during a three-month window in 2016, so our findings reflect a temporal snapshot. By 2016, voice calls were already in decline relative to data-based messaging (e.g., WhatsApp), meaning our sample is further selected towards users who still made voice calls regularly; this compounds the representativeness problem beyond carrier market share alone. Fifth, the naive-to-MRP comparison conflates demographic reweighting with the log-scale back-transformation (geometric vs. arithmetic mean), so the reported shifts should not be interpreted as purely demographic corrections. Finally, this study focuses on representativeness bias, but other sources of bias may also affect mobility estimates. In particular, heterogeneity in call behavior potentially correlated with socioeconomic status may influence the measurement of mobility itself, as individuals who generate more events are more likely to have their movements accurately captured. This type of bias is not addressed in the current framework.

Future work could explicitly account for this mechanism by extending the model to jointly incorporate mobility outcomes and call activity within a hierarchical framework. Another promising direction would be to leverage external data sources that are known to be unbiased, even if not fully representative, to calibrate or adjust mobility estimates, in a spirit similar to (Hsiao et al., 2024).

8 Conclusion

We have demonstrated that CDR data from a single carrier can have substantial socioeconomic representativeness bias, and that this bias translates into distorted aggregate mobility estimates. Multilevel regression and poststratification provides a principled, well-understood correction that leverages census data to reweight model-based predictions to the target population.

The framework can be adopted by researchers working with any form of non-representative passively collected data where the source of non-representativeness is known. To facilitate adoption, we release `mobmrp`, an open-source Python library implementing the full pipeline (data preparation, model fitting, poststratification, and validation) for use with arbitrary CDR and census datasets.¹ As mobile phone data continue to inform policy decisions about urban planning, transportation, and public health, accounting for who is and is not observed in the data is a matter of both scientific rigor and equity.

¹<https://github.com/leoferres/mobmrp>

Funding

This research was supported by FONIS grant SA24I0124 to L.F. L.F. also acknowledges financial support from the Lagrange Project of the Institute for Scientific Interchange Foundation (ISI Foundation), funded by the Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio di Torino (Fondazione CRT).

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A Full model equations

The model in Bambi formula notation:

```
log_avgROG ~ C(gse) + C(genero) + C(gse):C(genero)
            + C(is_weekday) + C(month)
            + (1 | comuna)
```

Default Bambi/PyMC priors are used throughout. The model is estimated with JAX-accelerated NUTS via the `numpyro` backend (4 chains, 2,000 post-warmup draws per chain) (Capretto et al., 2022; Salvatier, Wiecki, and Fonnesbeck, 2016).

B Secondary metrics

We fit the same multilevel model specification for two additional mobility metrics: Shannon entropy (S) and count of unique locations (U), both log-transformed. All models converge well (maximum $\hat{R} = 1.00$).

For entropy, the GSE coefficients (relative to ABC1) are: C2 -0.019 , C3 -0.043 , D -0.069 , E -0.086 ; men have higher entropy than women ($+0.089$). For unique locations: C2 -0.061 , C3 -0.073 , D -0.145 , E -0.180 ; men $+0.215$. Both metrics show a monotonically decreasing pattern from ABC1 to E, consistent with lower socioeconomic groups visiting fewer and less diverse locations. MRP corrections shift aggregate estimates in the same direction as for the radius of gyration.

C Sensitivity analysis details

Table 4: LOO-CV model comparison for log(ROG).

Model	ELPD	SE	p_{loo}
No interaction	-20,411.8	132.9	55.0
With interaction	-20,411.9	132.8	59.1
No random intercept	-20,966.8	129.3	14.8

D Robustness checks

D.1 Spatial assignment method

The baseline analysis assigns each user to the distrito of their home antenna (point-in-district). A natural alternative is to map each antenna to an H3 hexagonal cell at resolution 8 ($\approx 0.74 \text{ km}^2$), aggregate CDR values per hex cell, and redistribute them to distritos proportionally to the fraction of each hex cell overlapping each distrito (area-weighted redistribution).

We apply this alternative to the Santiago data. The two methods cover 451 and 424 distritos respectively; among the 420 distritos present in both, the Pearson correlation of district-level mean ROG is $r = 0.9999$. Refitting the full MRP model on the hex-weighted data, the maximum shift in any fixed-effect posterior mean is 0.036 log-units (GSE group C2), and all 94% credible intervals overlap with the baseline. Model convergence is identical ($\hat{R}_{\max} = 1.01$). We conclude that the results are insensitive to the spatial assignment method.

D.2 Population-weighted likelihood

Because the model is fit on cell-level averages, cells with few users are noisier than cells with many users but are treated identically in an unweighted likelihood. Section 4 specifies the residual as $\varepsilon_{ijkmt} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2/n_{ijkmt})$, which down-weights small cells. Here we verify that this choice does not drive the results by comparing the weighted specification against an unweighted baseline ($\varepsilon_{ijkmt} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$).

The maximum shift in any fixed-effect posterior mean between the two models is 0.104 log-units (approximately 11% on the ROG scale), concentrated in the GSE main effects. The gender coefficient shifts by 0.003 log-units, and GSE \times gender interactions shift by 0.003 to 0.044 log-units. All 94% credible intervals overlap substantially. The direction and ordering

of all effects are unchanged. We use the weighted specification as the default because it is the more principled treatment of aggregated data.

D.3 Cross-validation for unseen comunas

The five-fold CV in Section 6 holds out entire comunas. For a held-out comuna, no likelihood information updates its random intercept during training. The unknown intercept is drawn from the posterior of the group-level distribution:

$$\alpha_{j^*} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \hat{\sigma}_{\text{comuna}}^2), \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{comuna}}^2$ is itself a posterior quantity learned from the observed comunas. This marginalises over the unknown group intercept rather than setting it to zero or using a plug-in estimate, producing prediction intervals that are appropriately wider for unseen comunas than for observed ones.

To illustrate this empirically, we hold out five comunas (two large: 1,678 and 1,194 cells; three small: 119, 98, and 60 cells), fit the model on the remaining 42, and generate predictions for the held-out data. We then evaluate how often the true observed values fall within the model’s 94% prediction intervals. Across the 3,149 held-out cells, 91% of the observed values lie within these intervals, which is close to the expected 94%. When results are aggregated at the GSE-group and comuna levels, all observed values fall within the corresponding prediction intervals.